

the appropriate tetrahydrocarbazole (VIII) was obtained. These on dehydrogenation with 10% Pd-C in alcohol furnished the desired carbazoles. The reaction is schematically represented as follows and the properties of the reaction products are detailed in the Table 1.

References

1. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, B. P. DAS, *Science and Culture*, 1966, 32, 181.
2. D. P. CHAKRABORTY, B. P. DAS, K. C. DAS and B. C. DAS, Proc. IUPAC Symp. on Natural Products, 1966, p. 182.
- 3(a) D. P. CHAKRABORTY, A. ISLAM and P. BHATTACHARYYA, Proc. IUPAC Symp. on the Chemistry of Natural Products, 1972, p. 2.
- (b) A. ISLAM, P. BHATTACHARYYA and D. P. CHAKRABORTY, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Comm.*, 1972, 537.
- (c) D. P. CHAKRABORTY, B. P. DAS and S. P. BASAK, *Plant Biochem. J.*, 1974, 11, 73.
4. (Mrs.) F. ANWER, R. S. KAPIL and S. P. POPLI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 959.
5. K. C. DAS and BORIS WEINSTEIN, *J. Medicine Chem.*, 1972, 14, 1021.
6. D. P. CHAKRABORTY and B. K. CHOWDHURY, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, 33, 1265.

Potentiometric Study of the Complexes of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) with Schiff Base Derived from Sulphaphenazole and Salicylaldehyde

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CONDENSATION products of sulphonamides with salicylaldehyde have been found to be good bacteriostatic^{1,2} as well as good complexing agents³⁻⁶. Therefore it was decided to synthesise sulphaphenazole salicylaldehyde (SPHSA) and to study complex formation of SPHSA with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) potentiometrically.

Experimental

All chemicals employed were of Analar grade. Metal perchlorates were prepared and analysed as reported earlier⁴. SPHSA was prepared by the method described earlier⁴.

The Calvin Bjerrum pH titration technique^{7,8} as used by Irving and Rossotti⁹ has been applied to determine protonation constant of the ligand and formation constants of complexes.

The experimental procedure involved potentiometric titration against sodium hydroxide (CO₂ free) of the three mixtures. Set 1. Perchloric acid; Set 2. Perchloric acid+SPHSA Set 3. Perchloric acid+SPHSA+Metal solution.

Such that the concentration of the common ingredients were identical in different solutions, neutral sodium perchlorate solution was added so as to maintain ionic strength 0.2M. A pH meter (Beckmann model H2) was used for pH measurement.

To calculate the formation constant of the ligand proton system and values of n_A at different pH values were calculated using Set 1 and Set 2 titration curves. The ligand protonation formation curve was obtained by plotting the graph between n_A values and pH. $\bar{n}$ values were calculated using Set 2 and Set 3 titration curves. The metal-ligand stability constants were obtained from the analysis of metal-ligand formation curves drawn between $\bar{n}$ and pH.

Results and Discussion

From the titration curves it is observed that metal ligand curve is well separated from the ligand titration curves which proves that the liberation of protons is due to chelation. Least square method was applied to determine the metal-ligand stability constants. The values at an ionic strength ($\mu=0.2M$) have been summarised in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Ion	Log K_1	Log K_2	Log β	Log K_1/K_2	ΔG Kcal/mole	σ
H	Log $\beta^H = 6.2$					
Cu(II)	5.64	3.24	8.88	2.40	-12.13	± 0.0005
Ni(II)	5.20	2.68	7.88	2.52	-10.75	± 0.0013
Co(II)	4.60	1.82	6.42	2.78	- 8.77	± 0.0110

The result reveals that condensation products Cu(II), Ni(II) and Co(II) form complexes with SPHSA and the sequence of stability is Cu>Ni>Co which is in accordance with Irving and Williams¹⁰.

The large difference between successive stability constants may be attributed to the greater steric hindrance offered by SPHSA than coordinated water molecules.

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References

1. TAKEO TSUKAMATO and KENNOSUKE YUHI, *Yakugaku Zasshi*, 1958, 78, 706; *Chem. Abs.*, 1958, 52, 14561b.
2. TAKEO TSUKAMATO, Takeda Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd., Japan, 1960, 5766; *Chem. Abs.*, 1961, 55, 5879f.
3. R. R. GUPTA and R. KAUSHAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 385.
4. P. JAIN and K. K. CHATURVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 805.
5. P. JAIN and K. K. CHATURVEDI, *J. Inorg. Nuclear. Chem.* 1976, 38, 799.
6. P. JAIN and K. K. CHATURVEDI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, 52, 1220, 1225.
7. J. BJERREUM, 'Metalamine Formation in Aqueous Solution', Haese, Copenhagen.
8. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.
9. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
10. H. IRVING and R. J. P. WILLIAM, *Nature*, 1948, 162, 749.